

Utilization of Financial Technology Through Capital and Financial Literacy: A Study of Troso Jepara Weaving Artificial MSMEs

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ABSTRACT

This study analyzes the impact of relational capital and financial literacy on fintech adoption. The background of this study is the imbalance between the rapid pace of fintech innovation and the slow rate of equitable adoption, especially among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs). Data from 195 Troso Jepara Weaving MSME respondents were collected through questionnaires and processed using multiple linear regression methods to test the relationship between variables. The results of the analysis show that financial literacy significantly influences fintech adoption. This finding confirms that an adequate understanding of financial concepts is a crucial prerequisite for fostering individual confidence and willingness to adopt digital financial services. Furthermore, relational capital also positively and significantly influences fintech adoption. This underscores the important role of social networks and trust in facilitating technology adoption, where information originating from trusted sources can minimize uncertainty and build confidence among potential users.

KEYWORDS: Financial Technology, Financial Literacy, Relationship Capital

INTRODUCTION

In an increasingly fierce business competition era, every company must have a competitive advantage. This requires proactive and highly competitive management that effectively plans, organizes, directs, and controls company resources. Merthayasa et al. (2024) state that the sustainable development goals of SMEs impact business operational strategies and performance. In this case, SMEs must continually develop to keep up with developments and innovations in the market. This effort is key to maintaining and increasing sales value in the market. At the same time, improving business competition also positively impacts national economic growth. The Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) sector is vital to Indonesia's economic development. As one of the main pillars of the economy, the contribution of MSMEs to Gross Domestic Product (GDP) is significant, making it a strategic sector to drive the growth and stability of the country's economy.

Troso Weaving MSME is one of the MSMEs in Jepara Regency, with approximately 600 MSMEs operating as entrepreneurs and artisans. (Nurfaizah, 2023) This is also an important foundation for maintaining and improving the existence of Troso Woven MSMEs. Rapid technological developments have transformed the financial industry landscape, leading to innovations known as financial

technology (fintech). Fintech, such as digital payment services, online loans, and micro-investments, offers greater convenience, efficiency, and accessibility to the broader community. (Bank Indonesia, 2024). However, the adoption of this technology, especially among Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs), still faces various challenges. While fintech services are technically easy to access, non-technical factors often pose significant barriers to adoption..

Two important factors strongly suspected of playing a central role in determining the level of fintech adoption are financial literacy and relationship capital. Financial literacy refers to an individual's ability to understand and effectively use various financial skills, including personal financial management, decision-making, and understanding financial concepts. (Lusardi, A., & Mitchell, 2011). Piyani et al. (2023). In their research, they explained that financial literacy influences business continuity. Firlir & Fanesa (2022). His research also states that financial literacy positively and significantly influences fintech usage. Low levels of financial literacy often lead individuals to hesitate and fear using fintech services, as they do not fully understand the benefits, risks, or how they work. Conversely, individuals with high financial literacy tend to be more confident and able to utilize fintech optimally.

On the other hand, relationship capital, a part of social capital, refers to the social networks, trust, and norms of reciprocity that individuals or groups possess. (Nahapiet & Ghoshal, 2009). In MSMEs, relationship capital can be realized through trust among fellow business actors, good relationships with customers, suppliers, or local communities. These networks serve as credible sources of information and effective channels for socialization. When MSMEs see their colleagues or acquaintances successfully using fintech services, their trust will increase, reducing hesitation and motivating them to adopt similar technologies. In other words, relationship capital acts as a social bridge that facilitates the transfer of knowledge and trust, which is crucial in the technology adoption decision-making process. Chatterjee et al. (2023) were examining the role of intellectual capital, which includes sharing knowledge in digital form, producing intellectual capital that influences financial technology.

Although previous research has discussed the influence of financial literacy on fintech use, other studies have also linked relationship capital to business success. (Hamidah et al., 2020), There are still theoretical gaps that need to be filled. Most studies tend to analyze these two variables separately. Therefore, this study aims to comprehensively analyze the influence of financial literacy and relationship capital on the use of financial technology. By understanding the interaction of these two factors, more effective strategies can be found to encourage fintech adoption, particularly among Troso Weaving MSMEs, to increase financial inclusion and digital economic competitiveness.

I. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design

This study uses a quantitative approach with a causal explanatory design to investigate hypotheses regarding causal relationships between the variables studied. Specifically, this study analyzes the influence of relationship capital and financial literacy on adopting financial technology (fintech). This design was chosen based on its ability to collect measurable data and statistically validate causal relationships.

B. Research Population and Sample

The research population was 600 Troso Weaving MSMEs in Jepara Regency. Sample determination using the Slovin formula was used as a practical approach to calculate sample size based on the level of inaccuracy (tolerance) (Chandrari, 2017). This study used a 5% margin of error, resulting in a minimum sample size of 240 respondents. This study successfully collected 195 questionnaires suitable for analysis. Although this number is below the target, the sample is considered adequate and representative. This decision is supported

by statistical literature that suggests a sample size of more than 100 is sufficient for analysis. Sampling used a purposive sampling method by selecting actively producing MSMEs that meet the respondent criteria.

C. Data Collection Techniques

The procedure for collecting data is crucial because valid data is essential for a study to produce valid conclusions. To prove the validity of the hypothesis, proper data collection is essential. The data collection procedures for this study are as follows: Literature review and expert consultation, studying and approaching MSMEs, Building and leveraging good relationships with respondents and their environment, Pilot study, formulating and compiling questions, and Cross-checking validity and reliability.

D. Data Analysis Techniques

This study uses a quantitative data analysis method with the SEM PLS (Structural Equation Modeling - Partial Least Squares) approach. SEM PLS was chosen because of its ability to test structural and measurement models simultaneously, especially in conditions where the data is not normally distributed and the sample size is relatively small. This analysis will be conducted using Smart PLS software.

II. RESULT

Model measurement of this research uses indicators reflective of each variable, namely Relation Capital (X1), Financial Literacy (X2), and Fintech (Y). To test the validity of the indicator-indicator, the criterion value factor loading found in the outer loading table is used. This approach is relevant because in the reflective model, each indicator is considered as a manifestation of the construct underlying it. The outer loading test aims to identify whether each question item (indicator) in the questionnaire significantly contributes to the variable it represents. A low outer loading value indicates that the indicator is less effective in reflecting the intended construct. Conversely, a high value indicates that the indicator is valid in measuring the relevant latent construct (J. F. Hair et al., 2018). Ghozali (2015) states that an indicator is considered valid if its loading factor is above 0.70. However, a loading factor of 0.50–0.60 is still acceptable for exploratory research or the initial stages of instrument development. Therefore, in this study, the outer loading evaluation was conducted based on the following provisions: Outer loading value > 0.70 > indicator is declared valid, Outer loading value < 0.70 > the indicator is declared invalid and needs to be reviewed or eliminated. The outer loading value of each indicator in this study is shown in the following table.:

Table 1. Loading Factor Values

No	Indicator	Loading Factor	Information
1	KL	0,923	Valid
2	PM	0,928	Valid
3	RS	0,885	Valid
4	YP	0,892	Valid
5	X1.1	0,877	Valid
6	X1.2	0,889	Valid
7	X1.3	0,856	Valid
8	X1.4	0,878	Valid
9	X1.5	0,727	Valid
10	X2.01	0,809	Valid
11	X2.02	0,763	Valid
12	X2.03	0,796	Valid
13	X2.04	0,809	Valid
14	X2.05	0,774	Valid

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the convergent validity analysis results, all indicators used in this study, from the independent to the dependent variables, were declared valid. This is because the outer loading values of all indicators met the established criteria, namely above the threshold of 0.7. Average variance extracted (AVE) is a coefficient used to assess how much of the variance of indicators can be explained by the

latent construct that measures it. AVE reflects the ability of a latent construct to explain the average variance of its indicators, making it one of the primary measures used to evaluate convergent validity. (Ghozali, 2015). The recommended AVE value is at least 0.50. This value indicates that the latent construct can explain more than 50 percent of the variance in its indicators.

Table 2. Test Results Average Variance Extracted

Variabel	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
<i>Financial Technology</i>	0,823
<i>Financial Literacy</i>	0,625
<i>Relation Capital</i>	0,718

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the results of convergent validity testing, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value for the Financial Technology variable was 0.823, Financial Literacy was 0.625, and Relationship Capital was 0.718. All AVE values are above the minimum threshold of 0.50. This indicates that each construct can explain its indicators well, indicating that the relationship between the latent construct and its measuring indicators is strong, consistent, and successfully meets the AVE criteria. Discriminant validity aims to ensure that each latent construct in the model measures a concept distinct from the other constructs. In this context, discriminant validity indicates that indicators within one construct do not correlate highly with other theoretically distinct constructs. (Ghozali, 2015). The Fornell-Larcker

Criterion test examines the relationship between variables within a construct. This stage involves two testing methods: the correlation between variables and themselves, and the correlation between variables and other variables. In the Fornell-Larcker Criterion test, each variable's Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value is evaluated. The AVE value must be greater than the correlation between the construct and other constructs. In other words, the AVE of a variable must be greater than its correlation with other variables within the same construct. If the AVE value does not meet this requirement, the internal correlation between variables within the construct is considered low and does not meet the Fornell-Larcker criterion.

Table 3. Fornell-Larcker Criterion Test

Variabel	Financial Literacy	Financial Technology	Relation Capital
Financial Literacy	0,790		
Financial Technology	0,693	0,907	
Relation Capital	0,628	0,689	0,848
Financial Literacy	0,790		

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

From the table above, it can be seen that the correlation values between one variable and another variable show higher numbers. Therefore, it can be concluded that the Fornell-Larcker test criteria have been met. Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) This method calculates the ratio between

the correlation between a variable and other variables and the correlation between a variable and itself (heterotrait-monotrait ratio). If this ratio is less than 0.90, the cutoff value is used, and discriminant validity is met. (Garson, 2016).

Table 4. Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT)

Variabel	Financial Literacy	Financial Technology	Relation Capital
Financial Literacy			
Financial Technology	0,772		
Relation Capital	0,713	0,752	

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the table above, the HTMT value for each variable is less than 0.9, so each variable meets the HTMT prerequisites and meets Discriminant Validity. Cross-loading is comparing the loading value of an indicator on its own construct with the loading value of that indicator on

another construct. Discriminant validity is considered met if the indicator's loading value on its original construct is higher than its loading value on the other construct. The cross-loading value for each indicator can be seen in the table below:

Table 5. Cross Loading Values for Each Indicator

Indicator	Financial Literacy	Financial Technology	Relation Capital
KL	0,639	0,923	0,657
PM	0,630	0,928	0,588
RS	0,626	0,885	0,613
YP	0,621	0,892	0,638
X1.1	0,560	0,611	0,877
X1.2	0,503	0,587	0,889
X1.3	0,583	0,576	0,856
X1.4	0,561	0,620	0,878
X1.5	0,448	0,516	0,727
X2.01	0,809	0,600	0,531
X2.02	0,763	0,467	0,427
X2.03	0,796	0,486	0,497
X2.04	0,809	0,564	0,513
X2.05	0,774	0,597	0,503

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the results of the discriminant validity test using the cross-loading method, it can be concluded that each indicator has the highest correlation with the construct it measures compared to other constructs. Reliability testing aims to assess the internal consistency of indicators in representing a latent construct. This study measured

construct reliability using two leading indicators: Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha. According to Ghazali (2015), A construct can be declared reliable if its Composite Reliability value exceeds 0.70 and its Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds 0.70. These two measurements indicate that the indicators in the construct can provide consistent results

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in measurements and have good internal stability. According to J. Hair et al. (2019), it is a more accurate measure of reliability than Cronbach's Alpha because it considers the actual weight of each indicator in a latent construct. Composite Reliability assesses the extent to which indicators within a construct consistently measure the same

construct. A construct is considered reliable if the Composite Reliability value exceeds 0.70. However, for exploratory research or the initial stages of instrument development, a value above 0.60 is still acceptable. The higher the Composite Reliability value, the higher the indicator's internal consistency in measuring the construct.

Table 6. Composite Reliability Results for Each Variable

Variabel	Composite reliability (ρ_a)	Composite reliability (ρ_c)
Financial Technology	0,929	0,949
Financial Literacy	0,855	0,893
Relation Capital	0,905	0,927

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the test results, all variables in this study have a Composite Reliability value above 0.70, indicating that each construct's items can explain the latent variables reliably and consistently. Cronbach's Alpha is a statistical coefficient used to measure internal consistency between indicators

within a construct. Its value ranges from 0 to 1, with values above 0.70 indicating good reliability. (J. Hair et al., 2019; Garson, 2016). If a construct's Cronbach's Alpha value exceeds 0.70, then the construct is considered reliable and suitable for use in research. (J. Hair et al., 2019).

Table 7. Cronbach's Alpha Values for Each Variable

Variabel	Cronbach's Alpha
Financial Technology	0,928
Financial Literacy	0,850
Relation Capital	0,900

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

The table above shows that all variables in this study have values above 0.70, indicating that each construct has a good level of internal consistency. Thus, all variables can be declared reliable and suitable for further analysis in this study. The inner model encompasses the relationships between latent variables measured by indicators and how these latent variables influence each other within the context

of the constructed model. The purpose of inner model analysis is to test hypotheses regarding the relationships between variables and to understand how constructs interact within the research model. In this study, inner model analysis examines the R-square, T-statistic (hypothesis test), and Q-square values.

Figure 1. Inner Model Test Model

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

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R-squared is a statistical indicator used to assess how much an independent variable can explain the variation of the dependent variable in a structural model. The R-Square values for each dependent variable in this study are summarized in the following table:

Table 8. R Square Test Results

Variabel	R Square	R Square Adjusted
<i>Financial Technology</i>	0,587	0,582

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the test results, the R Square value for the Financial Technology variable was 0.587. This indicates that. In comparison, the independent variables in the model can explain 58.7% of the variation in the Financial Technology construct; other factors outside the model explain the remaining 41.3%. Model fit evaluation is conducted to assess the extent to which the constructed structural model can represent the data as a whole. In the SmartPLS approach, one of the indicators used to assess model suitability is the Standardized Root Mean Square

Residual (SRMR). SRMR measures the average standardized difference between the observed covariance and the covariance predicted by the model. The smaller the SRMR value, the smaller the difference between the actual value and the model estimate, indicating a good fit for the data. An SRMR value <0.100 indicates a good fit for the model and can be considered suitable for interpretation and conclusions (Henseler et al., 2016). The following are the results of the Model fit test :

Table 9. Model Fit Outputs

Indicator	Saturated Model	Estimated Model
SRMR	0,057	0,057
d_ ULS	0,338	0,338
d_ G	0,189	0,189
Chi-Square	218,272	218,272
NFI	0,891	0,891

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

The table above shows that the SRMR value for the saturated model is $0.057 < 0.100$, and the estimated model is $0.057 < 0.100$, so the model formed is declared to meet model feasibility. Structural Model Bootstrapping Test: Hypothesis testing in this study was conducted using a bootstrapping procedure on a structural model. This analysis evaluates the relationships between latent constructs through

statistical significance testing. Bootstrapping results allow researchers to assess the direction of positive or negative influence and the significance level of each relationship path in the model. Thus, this test provides a strong basis for evaluating whether the hypotheses proposed in the study are supported by empirical data (Garson, 2016). The following are the results of the bootstrapping path coefficients test. :

Table 10. Hypothesis Test Results

Information	Original sample (O)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values	Hipotesis	Information
<i>Relation Capital -> Financial Technology</i>	0,418	5,840	0,000	H1	Accepted
<i>Financial Literacy -> Financial Technology</i>	0,431	6,535	0,000	H2	Accepted

Source: SmartPls Output, (2025)

Based on the tests carried out, the following results are shown: The Influence of Relationship Capital on Financial Technology. The test results show a T-statistic value of 5.840 and a P-value of 0.000. With a p-value less than 0.05 and a t-statistic greater than 1.96, Hypothesis 1 is accepted.

This indicates that Relationship Capital has a significant effect on Financial Technology. The Influence of Financial Literacy on Financial Technology. Based on the test results, the T-statistic value was 6.535, and the P-value was 0.000. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 and the t-statistic is

greater than 1.96, Hypothesis 2 is accepted. This indicates that Financial Literacy has a significant influence on Financial Technology.

III. DISCUSSION

The results of this study indicate that relational capital has a positive and significant impact on the utilization of FinTech services. This finding indicates that the stronger the trust, relationship quality, and social support perceived by users, the greater their tendency to adopt financial technology. This conclusion aligns with previous research. For example, research conducted by Chatterjee et al. (2023) examines the role of intellectual capital in digital knowledge sharing, resulting in intellectual capital, where relational capital is one of the elements influencing financial technology. Theoretically, this finding can be explained through social capital theory (Putnam, 2020), which states that trust, norms, and social networks can facilitate coordination and increase acceptance of innovation. In the FinTech context, trust built through good relationships with service providers, community support, and perceptions of the company's reputation can reduce the uncertainty and risk perceived by users. This fosters confidence that FinTech services are safe, reliable, and suitable for everyday financial activities. A Study by Andini & Hariyani (2024) found that trust significantly influences the adoption of FinTech services among Generation Z in Indonesia. Study Rufaidah (2025) also emphasized that trust is a key factor in encouraging people to use FinTech services despite the inherent risks. A study by Wijaya et al. (2024) on GoPay usage in Indonesia shows that the quality of relationships with service providers and the level of trust significantly influence loyalty in digital payment applications. Therefore, this study's findings reinforce the view that relationship capital is crucial for encouraging FinTech adoption. FinTech providers that successfully build trust, maintain good communication, and foster long-term relationships with their users will more easily increase adoption rates and the sustainability of their services.

This study also found that financial literacy significantly and positively influences FinTech adoption. This suggests that a better understanding of digital financial products and services increases interest in and actual use of these technologies. Theoretically, these results align with the Financial Literacy Theory developed by Lusardi, A., & Mitchell (2011). This theory argues that financial literacy empowers individuals to make more rational and informed decisions. In the context of FinTech, this literacy includes evaluating the security of digital transactions, understanding hidden fees, and comparing various products. Individuals with good financial literacy will be more confident using FinTech services because they can assess risks and maximize benefits. This relationship can also be explained through the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) by Ajzen

(1991). This theory states that intentions, attitudes, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control influence behavior. Financial literacy increases perceived behavioral control, making individuals feel knowledgeable enough to manage their financial decisions. This encourages them to be more proactive in trying and continuing to use FinTech services.

This finding is consistent with various empirical studies. et al. (2025). Membuktikan states that digital financial literacy drives FinTech adoption in various countries. Aftab Aftab, et al (2025) found that financial literacy can reduce behavioral bias, facilitating wiser adoption. The study (Umar et al, 2025) also shows that financial literacy accelerates the adoption of digital innovations, such as central bank digital currencies (CBDCs). A study by Hamidah et al. (2020) confirms the significant influence of financial literacy on FinTech interest and usage among students and the general public. In short, these results reinforce the view that financial literacy is not merely cognitive capital but also a crucial catalyst for the financial sector's digital transformation. FinTech service providers should invest in financial education, information transparency, and features that help users understand the products.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the test results, this study concluded that relational capital and financial literacy significantly increase FinTech utilization among Troso Woven MSMEs. These findings confirm that technical aspects do not solely influence financial technology acceptance, but are also influenced by cognitive and social factors. First, financial literacy emerged as a primary factor driving FinTech adoption. Adequate knowledge of digital financial instruments and concepts provides Troso Woven MSMEs with confidence and the ability to assess the benefits and risks of FinTech services, thus encouraging them to utilize them more optimally. Second, relational capital also proved to play a significant role. Trust, social networks, and norms of reciprocity within the Troso Woven MSME community serve as a means to disseminate information and build confidence. Support or recommendations from trusted parties can reduce uncertainty and psychological barriers, thereby increasing the opportunities for Troso Woven MSMEs to adopt digital financial services..

Thus, this research provides both theoretical and practical contributions. From a theoretical perspective, these results strengthen the technology adoption model by integrating the roles of social and cognitive factors. Meanwhile, from a practical perspective, these findings demonstrate that efforts to increase financial inclusion in the Troso Weaving MSME sector need to be comprehensive, namely by improving financial literacy through formal

education while leveraging social networks to build trust and accelerate FinTech adoption.

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